

Developing children’s statistical understandings in the *Engaging with Beekeepers Using Data Science (BUDS)* project

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The BUDS project situates statistics learning within a real-world STEM context and prepares children for the fast-emerging field of Data Science. Sensors placed within beehives capture and stream data about in-hive conditions (humidity, sound, temperature) to classrooms via web technologies. Using lesson study, teacher educators and 27 pre-service primary teachers designed, taught, revised and retaught a series of five extended data lessons to two 6th classes in a culturally and linguistically diverse city school. The series of connected lessons raised awareness of the importance and plight of the honeybee and developed statistical and data science skills through engagement with sensor data. Children explored distributions of data, identified data landmarks, and utilised measures of central tendency and variation to describe and compare data from two different beehives. The study provides compelling evidence of the capabilities of young children to grapple with big statistical ideas, such as statistical association and informal inference, when provided with big data about real world problems.

Keywords: Integrated STEM, Data Science, statistical reasoning, pollinators

Introduction

The function and purposes of statistics education are fast evolving and extend beyond school-level curricular goals. Many goals of statistics education, such as enabling students to critically ‘read and write the world’ (Freire, 1970, p. 4) and promote the development of critical citizenship (Skovmose, 2011) by deepening understandings of issues of global importance, are shared goals of STEM education. STEM education is the purposeful integration of the STEM disciplines to solve complex, real-world problems and “innovate to solve them” (Balka, 2011, p. 7). In this paper, we show how primary children can be supported to analyse meaningful real-world data and to utilise their evolving statistical and graphical understandings to reflect upon broader societal issues and start their journey to becoming active citizens and positive agents of change (Gutstein, 2016).

Background and study context

Many policy initiatives have been developed to protect pollinators. The UN Sustainable Development Goals¹ (SDGs) incorporate an emphasis on food security (‘zero hunger’) and biodiversity (‘life on land’). The EU Pollinators Initiative² presents strategic objectives and a set of actions to be taken by the EU and its Member States to address the decline of pollinators in the EU and contribute to global conservation efforts. More locally, the All-Ireland Pollinator Plan (2021-2025) brings together pollinator initiatives across the island. Evident across global policies and initiatives is recognition of the role of local communities in protecting pollinators and in making their land more pollinator friendly.

The emphasis on the plight of pollinators, in this case the honeybee, situates the study of school mathematics within an integrated STEM context and highlights the critical role of

¹ <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>

² https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/conservation/species/pollinators/index_en.htm

interdisciplinary contexts in supporting successful STEM learning. It presents a coherent integration of STEM disciplinary content and addresses the challenge of curricular overload by supporting learning across multiple domains. A focus on bees directly addresses the primary science (NCCA 2000) curriculum strands of ‘Living Things’ and ‘Environmental Awareness and Care’ through the emphasis on pollination, lifecycles, food chains, and habitats. The analysis of data collected through innovative technologies (see figure 1) and a web-based data science tool (Common Online Data Analysis Platform, CODAP³) and interrogated using online data analytic tools targets the ‘data and chance’ strand of the primary mathematics curriculum (NCCA 2000) and champions the key competency ‘being a digital learner’ identified in the Primary Curriculum Framework (NCCA 2023).

Figure 1

A beekeeper placing sensors in our two beehives

Methodology

Using Lesson Study, the researchers worked with 27 primary pre-service teachers (PST) to design, teach, revise and reteach a series of 5 extended lessons (for details of the research design see Hourigan and Leavy, 2019) focusing on the development of statistical reasoning within an integrated STEM context. The series of research lessons were taught across a three-week period in two 6th classes within a local school. The school was in an urban setting and represented high linguistic and cultural diversity with many children being EAL learners. Data collection methods included field notes, lesson plans, samples of children’s work, researcher observations, photographs, audio recordings of children’s group conversations, PST and researcher reflections, and PST group presentations. A systematic process of data analysis was undertaken where the raw data were initially organised into natural units using representative codes (Creswell 2009). Successive examinations of the data led to the identification of relationships between codes and subsequently the creation of overarching themes. Thus, data were analysed using a grounded theory approach, where the data steered the emerging theory. The study was granted ethics approval.

Five STEM extended lessons were taught: (1) Introduction to the *Honeybee*, pollinators and sustainability; (2) Using *central tendency* and *variability* to describe and summarise animal data; (3) Examining *distributions of data* – what are sound patterns within

³ <https://codap.concord.org>

bee hives? (4) *Comparing distributions* – Using variations in temperature across time and between the bee hives to identify an ‘at-risk’ beehive (5) Exploring *relationships between variables* – is there a relationship between temperature and sound in the beehives?

Findings and Conclusion

Preliminary analysis reveals insights into the statistical understandings of children (figure 2). Firstly, the *context of pollinators* facilitated deep and interconnected understandings of statistical measures and enabled sense-making and the development of meaningful inferences and decisions. For example, one child calculated ‘the average of the averages’ in an effort to make a reliable estimate, another described an outlier as “a loner, far away from home’, while others vehemently argued against the opening of the hive “until late in May otherwise the bees might die from the cold”. This use of real-world sensor data supported the development of sophisticated understandings of *variation* and the development of data-based (and contextual) inferences about factors that influenced fluctuations in data. Similar to findings of recent studies using statistical inquiry and technologies in primary contexts (Ben-Zvi et al., 2012; Hourigan & Leavy, 2021), children in this study demonstrated the ability to *reason about distributions* and coordinate understandings of central tendency and variability when making data comparisons and inferences. Challenges with *graphical literacy* emerged and involved conflating high frequency values with upper limits (confusing the mode as the maximum) and difficulties arising from moving between graphical representations. With regard to the latter, children tended to misinterpret what the variable (axes) represented, especially following engagement with time-series data as they misinterpreted higher range values on a line plot as indicating data collection points later in the day.

Our analyses revealed the *benefits accrued from the use of technologies*. Children were intrigued by how the sensors collected data and enjoyed the novelty of using laptops and software to analyse data. Of particular surprise was the motivational value arising from children’s interest in *making predictions* about statistical measures (central tendency, ranges, outliers, etc.) represented on the large A3 graph printouts and then checking these predictions using CODAP. Of equal importance were the *affective dimensions* and the high level of engagement and enthusiasm evident throughout the lessons. The use of emerging technologies to collect and analyse data promoted problem solving and critical thinking and provided these students with access to high-quality STEM learning. Our analyses also support what we know about the benefits of using simple *language-sensitive approaches*, such as visual representations and careful introduction of vocabulary, in supporting all learners in accessing mathematical learning. Finally, the study is a testament to the *power of child centred pedagogies in supporting children in accessing sophisticated statistical ideas* as was evidenced in their ability to explore the relationships between two variables, make informal inferences, and estimate lines of best fit between temperature and sound data.

Figure 2

Engaging in the analysis of beehive data collected from in-hive sensors

Alongside supporting the development of big statistical ideas, the BUDS project integrates content “into real world, rigorous and relevant learning experiences” (Vasquez, Sneider & Comer, 2013, p. 4), thus ensuring that students witness the potential of statistics to provide insights into both their future and the future of their communities.

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